

Retarded Time and Radiation from an Accelerated Charge

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The use of retarded time to indicate that a signal from a charge can only travel at a speed of c (the speed of light in any frame) so that a measurement at a point r (vector) at t is based on pieces of charge at various r' points sending signals at different times. In other words, there is the notion of a virtual photon in the electric and magnetic field system. The photon is virtual in the sense that it does not escape from the system.

In this note, we ask: Where does this photon appear? It is well-known that Maxwell wrote two wave-equations, one for E electric field and B magnetic field, using his electromagnetic equations with sources set to 0 (i.e. charge and current densities). A moving charge, however, has charge density and current. Here we suggest that one might see the presence of a virtual photon by examining the Lorentz gauge $d/dt \text{ partial } \phi + \text{grad dot } A = 0$ and by considering $\phi = \sum_k \exp(-i E(k)t + i k r)$, without $E(k)$ being explicitly defined. A similar expression holds for A . If one considers a point charge at rest and applies a Lorentz transformation, we argue that one obtains the dispersion relation: $E(k) + v k = 0$ if $v=c$. In other words, one obtains a photon dispersion relationship suggesting the presence of virtual photons in ϕ and A . It is these photons which may send signals. (Note: The presence of virtual photons in electromagnetism is well-known (1), although we do not know if the Lorentz gauge argument has been used before or not with respect to arguing their existence.)

Given the presence of virtual photons and the idea of a photon signal being sent from a charge, hence the notion of retarded time, we ask: Why does an accelerating charge emit photons and one moving at constant v (velocity) does not, when both systems use retarded time? We suggest, without using the usual argument that $E \times B$ has pieces that go as $1/(rr)$ in the accelerating case, that a piece of force is due to changes in the virtual photon signal and not to changes in the potential in r in the denominator, i.e. $1/r$, which is the usual force due to a charge. Thus, virtual (signal) photons are demonstrating a presence of their own, i.e. becoming real and escaping.. In (3), we called this a degree of freedom not associated with collective motion and likened it to temperature, except in this case, the energy of the photon disappears from the system.

The Presence of a Virtual Photon in an Electromagnetic System

It is well-known that Einstein used photons with a constant speed c in a vacuum (which does not change when seen from different constant velocity moving frames) to measure particles with rest mass. Physically, in the real world, such measurements using photons happen all of the time. Thus, the speed c appeared in his special relativistic results, i.e. Lorentz transformations. These Lorentz transformations, however, had already been found by Lorentz for Maxwell's electromagnetic equations using the requirement that the equations retain their form when viewed from different frames moving with constant velocities.

Before this time, Maxwell had found that if he set charge and charge current densities equal to zero in his equations, he could write two wave equations, one for the E electric field and the other for B , the magnetic field, and that such a wave traveled with a speed $c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$,

where ϵ_0 and μ_0 are two parameters in his equations. Thus, light was considered an electromagnetic wave (even though originally one required a charge to have E,B).

Here we ask: Are photons present in ϕ and A , the electric and magnetic vector potentials? The charge and charge current are not set to zero in this case. According to the literature (1), it is well-known that there are virtual photons in electromagnetism, but here we consider whether they appear due to the Lorentz gauge.

Lorentz Gauge and Virtual Photons

In electromagnetic theory:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } A \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \text{grad } \times A \quad ((1b))$$

Here we use SI units.

Using Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, it is argued in (2) that one may introduce the well-known Lorentz gauge condition:

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} + \text{grad } \cdot A = 0 \quad ((2))$$

This condition is derived starting with the Maxwell equation:

$$\text{Grad } \times B = \mu_0 J + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dE}{dt} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{So } \text{grad } \times B = \epsilon_{ijk} \partial_j \epsilon_{klm} \partial_l A_m = (\delta_{il} \delta_{jm} - \delta_{im} \delta_{jl}) \partial_j \partial_l A_m \quad \text{so}$$

$$\text{Grad } \{ \text{grad } \cdot A + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d\phi}{dt} \} = \mu_0 J - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} + \text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } A \quad ((4))$$

The idea of the Lorentz gauge is to suggest that the LHS of ((4)) is 0 through $\{ \text{grad } \cdot A + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d\phi}{dt} \} = 0$ so that the D'Alembertian of A equals $-\mu_0 J$.

Using this gauge, one may find a similar expression, namely D'Alembertian of $\phi = -\frac{1}{\epsilon_0}$ charge density ((5))

In other words, the Lorentz gauge allows one to write equations for A and ϕ which have a similar mathematical structure, i.e. D'Alembertian acting on an object = -constant * source of object.

Note; one may always write $A \rightarrow A + \text{grad } W$ where W is a scalar function, so there is freedom in changing A in a certain way provided that $\phi \rightarrow \phi - \frac{dW}{dt}$ ((4)) because of ((1a)).

We return to ((2)) and suggest writing ϕ and A as Fourier series using:

$$\phi = \sum_k \frac{1}{k} \exp(-i E_c t + i k x) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{and a similar expression for } A.$$

We next continue the case of a charge q at rest with an electrostatic potential ϕ .

Given that rest mass $(0, m_0)$ transforms to (p, m) , we suggest that $q\phi$ is energy and so $(0, q\phi)$ transforms to $(A, q\phi')$.

The Lorentz transformation matrix is:
$$\begin{vmatrix} g & gv/c \\ -vg/c & g \end{vmatrix} \quad ((7))$$

where $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$

Thus, $A_c = g v/c \phi$ for v in the x direction and $\phi' = g \phi$.

We use A_c because (pc, E) is the form of a 4-vector.

If one considers formal definitions of ϕ and A in terms of charge density for a constant velocity (5), then:

$\phi \rightarrow 1/\epsilon_0$ while $A \rightarrow u_0 v = 1/\epsilon_0 (u_0 \epsilon_0 v) = 1/\epsilon_0 (1/cc) v$

This is consistent with (A_c, ϕ) .

Using these values in the Lorentz gauge, with ϕ replaced with ϕ' , using the Fourier series ((6)) and collecting coefficients of $\exp(-i E t + i k x)$ one finds:

$0 = -E/cc + k 1/c (v/c)$ or $E = k v$ so setting $v=c$ yields $E=kc$ ((8))

((8)), however, is a wave dispersion relationship which applies to a photon.

Thus we suggest that photons are present in ϕ and A , and so also in the electric and magnetic fields E, B .

If virtual photons exist in ϕ and A , they may be used to send signals.

We also note that if one considers ((4)) with $j=0$ =current density and the Lorentz gauge, that one obtains:

D'Alembertian $A = 0$ ((9))

For each A_i , one has a wave-equation, suggesting that one may expand A in terms of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ with $E=pc$.

Consequences of Virtual Photons and Retarded Time

In the above section, we have suggested that virtual photons exist in electric and magnetic fields of a charged system and may be used to send signals to a measurement point. Thus, there seems to be some justification for using retarded time which is defined in the following way.

Imagine that one has a charge density($\rho(\mathbf{r}', t)$) ((10))

Let there exist a fixed origin, and a fixed measurement point \mathbf{r} vector, measured from the origin. Each piece of charge density (at various \mathbf{r}' vector) points contributes to the result at the measurement point. The distance from \mathbf{r}' vector to \mathbf{r} vector is:

$$R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'| \quad ((11))$$

The problem is that R is different for different \mathbf{r}' vector positions and if one imagines that a signal is sent from each \mathbf{r}' vector points to \mathbf{r} vector, with the speed is c (due to the virtual photon) which is the same as seen in any reference frame, then signals must be sent at different times. Hence the idea of a retarded time, i.e.

$$t \rightarrow t - R/c \quad ((12)) \quad \text{in the charge density.}$$

As a result, the charge density function is changed and the usual time piece now responds to spatial derivatives.

The idea of retarded time applies to both a charge moving at a constant speed and to one that is accelerating. The question we ask is: Why does an accelerating charge radiate photons?

The standard argument (5) for describing radiation from an accelerating charge is to calculate E and B and then $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$, the momentum density. This is multiplied by rr , the area of a sphere with r taken to infinite. If one obtains a finite result, this implies electromagnetic momentum is leaving the system, i.e. there is radiation which is attributed to photons.

The details of this calculation are given in (5) pages 458-459. Using retarded time leads to the form:

$$\Phi = \text{constant} \left(\frac{q}{r} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{p} / (rrr) + \mathbf{r} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} / (rr) \right) \quad ((13 a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$A = \text{constant} \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \quad ((13b))$$

Here \mathbf{p} is the dipole moment evaluated at the retarded time: $t - r/c$ (after an expansion) ((13c))

The main point is that when taking grad which appears in $\mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad} \Phi - d\mathbf{A}/dt$ partial, grad may act on r terms in the denominator, increasing their power in the denominator

by 1, or on the dipole moment p . For a constant velocity charge, dp/dt goes as qv , but a second derivative is 0, while for an accelerating charge, one has a nonzero value. Note from (5):

$$d/dr dp/dt \rightarrow 1/c d/dt dp/dt \quad ((14))$$

Thus, when calculating ϕ and A , one has terms in which the r in the denominator is not increased by 1. If one acts with d/dr on an r in the denominator, this implies the usual force from a charged object. Acting on dp/dt with d/dr , however, implies a contribution to force (E and B) due to the virtual photon carrying a signal.

We suggest this means the signal virtual photon is actually taking on an identity of its own (physical contribution to E and B) which is not of the nature of the force from a charge (d/dr acting on r in the denominator.)

In other words, the virtual photon is becoming a real photon which then leaves the system. We suggest that this means that the process of accelerating a charge must necessarily transfer energy to internal degrees of freedom (as in the case of heat generated by an object moving on a floor with friction). As a result, the radiation of an accelerating charge seems to also imply entropy increase because one cannot accelerate the charge system without transferring energy to single degrees of freedom, so to speak. We discussed these single degrees of freedom in (3).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first argue for the presence of virtual photons in ϕ and A , electrostatic and vector magnetic potentials by using the Lorentz gauge and ideas of a Lorentz transformation. If virtual photons are present, this may provide justification for the use of retarded time in calculations of moving charges. We next ask: Why does an accelerating charge radiate while a constant moving one does not? Virtual photons are used to send signals in both cases. The standard argument for photon radiation (5) is to calculate E and B and compute $E \times B$, the momentum density. This, multiplied by area ($4\pi r^2$ for a sphere), with r taken to infinite should be zero if there is no radiation and finite if there is. In the case of an accelerating charge it is finite.

We suggest that the reason that $E \times B$ has finite pieces is that virtual photons are becoming real and then leaving the system. This occurs because d/dr derivatives which usually act on $1/r$ type terms (yielding force due to charges) are now able to act on dp/dt (retarded time) where p is the dipole moment (i.e. $dp/dt = qv$). Acting on the retarded time argument, however, means considering force due to the virtual signal photon. Thus, these virtual signal photons now create physical force (i.e. E and B at a measurement point). We thus conclude that they are no longer virtual, but real. In other words, as in (3), we suggest that this is an entropic process like an object moving on a frictional surface. One cannot create/remove collective energy (motion of the charge system) without exciting individual degrees of freedom, i.e. converting virtual photons into real ones which then escape.

References

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